

Lightweight Lattice-Based Secure Communication Framework for Forward and Backward Secrecy in IoD Systems

Andreou Andreas
Department of Computer Science
University of Nicosia
Nicosia, Cyprus
andreou.andreas@unic.ac.cy

Constandinos X. Mavromoustakis
Department of Computer Science
University of Nicosia
Nicosia, Cyprus
mavromoustakis.c@unic.ac.cy

Evangelos Markakis
Department of Electrical and
Computer Engineering
Hellenic Mediterranean University
Heraklion, Crete, Greece
emarkakis@hmu.gr

Athina Bourdena
Department of Business Administration
and Tourism
Hellenic Mediterranean University
Heraklion, Crete, Greece
bourdena@hmu.gr

George Mastorakis
Department of Management Science
and Technology
Hellenic Mediterranean University
Agios Nikolaos, Crete, Greece
gmastorakis@hmu.gr

Abstract—Secure communication and data sharing in Internet of Drones (IoD) systems are critical to ensuring trust, privacy, and resilience in emerging applications. These systems face significant challenges, including risks of malicious data propagation, privacy breaches, and vulnerabilities to quantum attacks. This paper improves the Frodo Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM) to enable implicit authentication and asynchronous key negotiation. Building on this foundation, we propose a lightweight lattice-based secure communication framework tailored for IoD systems. Our framework achieves essential security objectives, including quantum resistance, forward and backward secrecy, and privacy preservation, effectively addressing these challenges. Additionally, we provide performance analysis, demonstrating that the proposed framework is lightweight and highly suitable for secure IoD deployments compared to existing alternatives.

Index Terms—Lightweight security, Lattice-based cryptography, FrodoKEM, Quantum resistance, IoD system security

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid advancements in Internet technologies, the Internet of Drones (IoD) has emerged as a transformative paradigm, enabling diverse applications such as traffic surveillance, disaster management, and environmental monitoring. IoD systems facilitate seamless data collection and exchange, driving innovation in critical infrastructures and smart services. However, the success of IoD systems depends on overcoming significant challenges related to security, privacy, and trust, in-

cluding vulnerabilities to malicious attacks, privacy breaches, and the increasing threat of quantum computing.

Researchers have proposed various mechanisms to ensure secure communication and data sharing within IoD environments, such as blockchain technology and post-quantum cryptographic schemes [1], [2]. Blockchain’s decentralized architecture and transparency offer potential solutions for secure and accountable data exchange [3]. Recent studies have introduced blockchain-based frameworks to mitigate risks such as malicious data propagation and to enhance data traceability [4], [5]. Despite these advancements, existing approaches remain limited by vulnerabilities to quantum attacks, inefficient key management, and performance constraints [6].

This paper addresses the challenges mentioned above by introducing a lightweight lattice-based secure communication framework designed for IoD systems. The proposed framework incorporates an improved Frodo Key Encapsulation Mechanism (FrodoKEM) to enable implicit authentication and asynchronous key negotiation [7], ensuring quantum resistance [8]. Also, it leverages blockchain technology to enhance accountability and mitigate privacy risks associated with data sharing in IoD environments.

The contributions include significant improvements to the FrodoKEM [9] to address challenges related to quantum resistance [10], while the development of the framework effectively

meets critical security and privacy requirements in IoD systems [11], [12]. It also ensures forward and backward secrecy while maintaining lightweight performance [13], making it highly suitable for IoD applications. Furthermore, a comprehensive security and performance analysis demonstrates the framework's resilience and practicality in addressing the unique demands of IoD environments.

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Learning with Errors

The Learning with Errors (LWE) problem is a computationally complex problem that forms the basis of many post-quantum cryptographic schemes, defined by (1)

$$b_i \equiv \mathbf{a}_i \cdot \mathbf{s} + e_i \pmod{q}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_i \in \mathbb{Z}_q^n$ is a vector over the integer ring modulo q , $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^n$ denote a secret vector, e_i is an error term sampled from a discrete Gaussian distribution or other specified error distribution, and b_i denotes the resulting noisy observation.

The goal is to recover the secret vector \mathbf{s} given the noisy observations (\mathbf{a}_i, b_i) . The hardness of the LWE problem lies in its equivalence to solving specific worst-case lattice problems, making it a strong candidate for post-quantum cryptography. Its security is further enhanced by parameter choices, such as the dimension n , modulus q , and the error term e_i distribution.

B. Frodo Key Encapsulation Mechanism

The FrodoKEM is a post-quantum key exchange protocol based on the hardness of the LWE problem. Proposed by Joppe Bos et al. [14], it ensures secure symmetric key establishment between two parties. The mechanism comprises four algorithms. First is the setup algorithm takes a security parameter λ as input and outputs the system public parameters (q, n, m, χ) , where q denotes the modulus, n the dimension of the secret vector, m is the number of samples, and χ is the error distribution.

The key generation algorithm takes the public parameters as input and outputs a public-private key pair (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{s}) , where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{m \times n}$ is a randomly generated matrix and $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^n$ is a secret vector sampled from χ .

The key exchange algorithm takes as input the public parameters, the private key of the first party (\mathbf{s}_1), and the public key of the second party (\mathbf{A}_2). Hence it computes (2) and (3)

$$\mathbf{b}_1 = \mathbf{A}_2 \cdot \mathbf{s}_1 + \mathbf{e}_1 \pmod{q}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{k}_1 = \text{Hash}(\mathbf{b}_1), \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{e}_1 is sampled from χ , and \mathbf{k}_1 is the common session key.

The fourth is the key recovery algorithm which takes as input the public parameters, the private key of the second party (\mathbf{s}_2), and the transmitted hint matrix (\mathbf{b}_1) and calculates (4)

Fig. 1. System Model

$$\mathbf{k}_2 = \text{Hash}(\mathbf{b}_1 - \mathbf{A}_1 \cdot \mathbf{s}_2), \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{k}_2 matches \mathbf{k}_1 under correct computation.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model illustrated in Fig. 1 represents a simplified model for the proposed framework. The key components include the Authorized Authority (AA), Registration Authority (RA), Blockchain Network, Edge Computing Nodes, Drone Clusters (DC), and IoD Users. The AA and RA manage system initialization, registration, and secure key distribution. DC, containing individual drones, interact with RA and nodes for real-time processing and communication. The Blockchain network securely stores transaction records and ensures accountability. Edge nodes provide localized data processing to reduce latency, while IoD users represent the end entities interacting with drones. The connections illustrate the secure communication pathways between entities, ensuring efficient and safe operation within the IoD system.

The framework addresses challenges unique to the IoD environment, including real-time data sharing, user privacy, and resilience against quantum threats. Implicit authentication is achieved during the key exchange process between drones, IoD nodes, and users without relying on additional cryptographic signatures. The scheme reduces computational costs while maintaining strong security guarantees by eliminating the overhead of signature-based authentication. This feature is particularly beneficial in resource-constrained IoD environments.

It also supports asynchronous key negotiation, allowing secure communication to proceed even when., drones or users

are offline. Let \mathbf{k}_A and \mathbf{k}_B represent the keys of two communicating parties. The session key $\mathbf{k}_{\text{session}}$ is derived using (5)

$$\mathbf{k}_{\text{session}} = \text{Hash}(\mathbf{k}_A \oplus \mathbf{k}_B), \quad (5)$$

where \oplus denotes the XOR operation; this ensures that the session key is securely established and remains unique for each communication session.

The scheme employs lattice-based cryptography, leveraging the hardness of the LWE problem. This approach ensures that the scheme is secure against attacks from quantum computers, making it future-proof in the face of advancing computational capabilities. Using lattice-based mechanisms is critical for IoD systems, where robust security is essential to protect sensitive operational data.

Forward and backward security are also fundamental features of the proposed scheme. Compromising a current session key does not affect the security of past or future communications. Formally, for any two sessions i and j where $i \neq j$, the session keys satisfy (6)

$$\mathbf{k}_i \neq \mathbf{k}_j. \quad (6)$$

Thus, it ensures that each session remains independent, preventing attackers from gaining unauthorized access to previous or subsequent communications.

Privacy preservation is another cornerstone of the scheme. Even if an attacker intercepts messages transmitted over public channels, they cannot extract sensitive information or user identities. The encrypted data \mathbf{c} is computed by (7)

$$\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{r} \pmod{q}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{m} represents the message, \mathbf{E} is the encryption key matrix, and \mathbf{r} is a random vector sampled from a specified distribution. Thus, it ensures that even intercepted data remains unintelligible without the decryption keys.

In addition, it supports traceability, identifying malicious users through their encrypted session records. Let $\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{c})$ represent the traceability function associated with the ciphertext \mathbf{c} . The identity of the user can be determined using (8)

$$\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{c}) = \text{ID}_{\text{user}}, \quad (8)$$

where ID_{user} is the unique identifier of the entity responsible for the malicious activity. This capability ensures accountability and supports the detection and mitigation of security threats within the IoD ecosystem.

IV. MODIFIED FRODOKEM

To satisfy the security requirements of IoD scenarios, including implicit authentication, forward secrecy, and backward secrecy, the FrodoKEM was modified. These improvements ensure secure and efficient communication in the dynamic and resource-constrained IoD environment.

The setup algorithm initializes the system parameters given by (9)

$$\text{pp} \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda) \quad (9)$$

where 1^λ is the security parameter, and the output pp represents the system public parameters given by (10)

$$\text{pp} = (q, n, \chi, b, \mathbf{A}), \quad (10)$$

where q is the modulus representing the ring of integers modulo, n denotes the matrix dimension, χ is a discrete Gaussian distribution over \mathbb{Z} with mean zero and standard deviation ρ , b denotes the bit length of the session key and $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$ is a common public matrix.

Two key generation algorithms are used for generating public-private key pairs (11)

$$\text{pk} \leftarrow \text{KGen}_1(\text{pp}, \text{sk}), \quad (11)$$

where $\text{sk} = \mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$ is a private key.

First sample an error matrix $\mathbf{E} \sim \chi$ over $\mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$. Then, compute the public key using (12)

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{E}, \quad \mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n} \quad (12)$$

and return $\text{pk} = \mathbf{B}$.

The second key generation is given by (13)

$$\text{PK} \leftarrow \text{KGen}_2(\text{pp}, \text{SK}), \quad (13)$$

where $\text{SK} = \mathbf{S}' \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$ is a private key.

For this step resample an error matrix $\mathbf{E}' \sim \chi$ over $\mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$ and compute the public key by (14)

$$\mathbf{B}' = \mathbf{S}' \cdot \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{E}', \quad \mathbf{B}' \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n} \quad (14)$$

and as after (12) return $\text{PK} = \mathbf{B}'$.

The key exchange algorithms generate session keys for secure communication between entities in the IoD framework using (15)

$$k \leftarrow \text{EKey}_1(\text{pp}, \text{key}_1, \text{key}_2), \quad (15)$$

where key_1 and key_2 are keys that can be either private or public.

Now we choose the sample of the noise matrix $\mathbf{E}'' \sim \chi$ over $\mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$ and calculate the session key by using (16)

$$k = \text{key}_1 \cdot \text{key}_2 + \mathbf{E}'' \quad (16)$$

Finally we have the Four-Key Exchange given by (17)

$$K \leftarrow \text{EKey}_2(\text{pp}, \text{key}_1, \text{key}_2, \text{key}_3, \text{key}_4), \quad (17)$$

where key_1 , key_2 , key_3 , and key_4 are keys that can be either private or public.

The sample of the noise matrix $\mathbf{E}^* \sim \chi$ over $\mathbb{Z}_q^{m \times n}$. Compute the session key by (18)

$$K = \text{key}_1 \cdot \text{key}_3 + \text{key}_2 \cdot \text{key}_3 + \text{key}_2 \cdot \text{key}_4 + \mathbf{E}^*. \quad (18)$$

The improvements ensure implicit authentication by embedding identity verification directly into the session key generation process, eliminating the need for additional cryptographic signatures. Furthermore, the scheme guarantees forward and backward secrecy, ensuring that the compromise of a session key does not compromise the security of previous or subsequent keys. Finally, the reliance on the LWE problem provides quantum resistance, offering robustness against adversaries equipped with quantum computing capabilities.

V. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The AA and RA initialize the system. The AA first generates and publishes the system public parameter $pp = (q, n, \chi, b, A)$ by inputting a security parameter λ and performing the setup algorithm $\text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$. Here q is the modulus of the ring of integers modulo q , n is the matrix dimension, χ denotes a discrete Gaussian distribution over \mathbb{Z}_q with mean zero and standard deviation ρ , b represents the bit length of the session key and $A \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$ is a standard public matrix.

The AA randomly selects a private key $S_{AA} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$ and executes the key generation algorithms $\text{KGen}_1(pp, S_{AA}) \rightarrow pk_{AA}$ and $\text{KGen}_2(pp, S_{AA}) \rightarrow PK_{AA}$. where pk_{AA} and PK_{AA} represent the public keys. The AA completes its initialization by obtaining the private-public key pair $(S_{AA}, pk_{AA}, PK_{AA})$. Similarly, the RA generates its private-public key pair $(S_{RA}, pk_{RA}, PK_{RA})$ following the same steps.

The registration phase involves registering IoD entities, such as drone clusters, individual drones, and ground users. A drone cluster C_i submits its identity, operational certificates, and other relevant information to the AA for registration. The AA verifies the information and generates a private key $sk_{C_i} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$. It then performs using (19) and (20)

$$\text{KGen}_1(pp, sk_{C_i}) \rightarrow pk_{C_i}, \quad (19)$$

$$\text{KGen}_2(pp, sk_{C_i}) \rightarrow PK_{C_i}, \quad (20)$$

providing the private-public key pair $(sk_{C_i}, pk_{C_i}, PK_{C_i})$ to C_i through a secure channel.

An individual drone D_i registers with both the AA and RA. The AA assigns a private key $sk_{D_i} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$ and computes (21) and (22)

$$\text{KGen}_1(pp, sk_{D_i}) \rightarrow pk_{D_i}, \quad (21)$$

$$\text{KGen}_2(pp, sk_{D_i}) \rightarrow PK_{D_i}. \quad (22)$$

Simultaneously, the RA distributes a signal key pair $(ssk_{D_i}, spk_{D_i}, sPK_{D_i})$ for secure signaling within the IoD network.

A ground user U_i registers by submitting identity and operational information to the AA. The AA assigns a private key $sk_{U_i} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{n \times n}$ and generates (23) and (24)

$$\text{KGen}_1(pp, sk_{U_i}) \rightarrow pk_{U_i}, \quad (23)$$

$$\text{KGen}_2(pp, sk_{U_i}) \rightarrow PK_{U_i}. \quad (24)$$

The RA also provides U_i with a batch of short-term key pairs $\{(esk_{U_i}^j, epk_{U_i}^j, ePK_{U_i}^j)\}_{j=1}^N$ for secure communication.

Communication between IoD entities begins with secure session establishment. For example, when a user U_i communicates with a drone D_i , they perform the key exchange algorithm using (25)

$$k_{UD} = \text{EKey}(pp, sk_{U_i}, PK_{D_i}), \quad (25)$$

where k_{UD} is the session key which ensures confidentiality and authenticity of the exchanged data.

After communication, drones share collected data which is encrypted using the session key (26)

$$ct_{data} = \text{Enc}_{k_{UD}}(data), \quad (26)$$

where Enc is a symmetric encryption algorithm. The ciphertext ct_{data} is transmitted securely over the IoD network.

The traceability phase ensures accountability within the IoD framework. In case of malicious activity, the AA and RA collaborate to trace the offending entity. By decrypting session messages with the relevant key pairs, the identity of the malicious entity can be determined using (27)

$$\mathcal{T}(ct) = \text{ID}_{entity}, \quad (27)$$

where \mathcal{T} is the traceability function and ID_{entity} represents the unique identifier of the offending entity.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Security Analysis

The implementation of implicit authentication is achieved through the use of each entity's private identity key during the key negotiation process. Thus, both parties' generation of the same session key serves as evidence of successful authentication. Confirm that the communication parties, such as a drone and a ground user, are mutually authenticated without requiring additional signature mechanisms.

The key negotiation process is asynchronous, as the key exchange algorithm only requires the receiver's public key as input. In addition, the drone cluster or IoD server can facilitate identity authentication, ensuring that both entities involved in the communication do not need to be online simultaneously. It is particularly advantageous when drones operate intermittently or in remote areas. It achieves quantum resistance using the improved FrodoKEM based on the LWE problem's hardness. Ensuring the key negotiation process remains secure against adversaries equipped with quantum computational capabilities, making the scheme robust for future IoD applications.

Forward and backward secrecy is also achieved by generating a new session key for each communication session. For example, a unique session key is negotiated whenever a ground user interacts with a drone. Even if an adversary

compromises a session key, it does not impact the security of previous or subsequent session keys, ensuring the confidentiality of all other communications. The scheme preserves privacy by ensuring that the identities of users and drones are not exposed on public channels. All exchanged data is encrypted before transmission, ensuring only the intended recipient can access it. For instance, telemetry data collected by a drone is encrypted before being shared with a ground user, preventing unauthorized access and maintaining data confidentiality.

Finally, it incorporates traceability to identify and mitigate malicious behaviour within the IoD framework. If an anomaly is detected, the AA and RA collaborate to calculate the session key and trace the identity of the malicious entity. This process ensures accountability and enhances the overall security of the system.

B. Performance Evaluation

Each cryptographic operation was executed 1000 times, and the average runtime was recorded. The average execution time of key cryptographic operations is presented in Table I. These results highlight the efficiency of post-quantum cryptographic primitives essential for secure IoD communications.

TABLE I
COST OF CRYPTOGRAPHIC OPERATIONS (μs)

Symbol	Operation	Cost (μs)
<i>KGen</i>	Key pair generation	731.401
<i>1EKey</i>	Single shared key computation	91.981
<i>3EKey</i>	Multi-party shared key computation	312.603
<i>Enc</i> _{AES/ECB}	Symmetric encryption (AES/ECB)	829.124
<i>Dec</i> _{AES/ECB}	Symmetric decryption (AES/ECB)	852.901

The computation overhead for different IoD entities during various operational phases is summarized in Table II. The analysis considers the AA, RA, DC, individual drone, and ground user. The results demonstrate the suitability of the proposed scheme for resource-constrained IoD devices.

TABLE II
COMPUTATION OVERHEAD (MS)

Phase	AA	RA	DC	Drone	Ground User
Initialization	1.358	1.358	-	-	-
Registration	4.451	$1.358(N+3)$	-	-	-
Data Collection	-	-	2.812	2.82	3.801
Data Sharing	-	-	2.812	2.82	4.483
Traceability	$0.291+0.851x$	-	-	-	-

* N denotes the number of temporary key pairs, and x represents the number of sessions for an illegal user.

The bar chart in Fig. 2 presents the execution times for critical cryptographic operations. Symmetric encryption and decryption using AES/ECB have the highest costs, at approximately 829.124 μs and 852.901 μs , respectively. These operations are essential for securing sensitive data but are computationally intensive. In contrast, the cost of single shared key computation (*1EKey*) is the lowest at 91.981 μs , demonstrating the efficiency of the proposed scheme for key establishment. Key generation (*KGen*) and multi-party shared

Fig. 2. Cost of Cryptographic Operations

key computation (*3EKey*) exhibit moderate costs, balancing security and computational performance. These results validate the lightweight nature of the cryptographic selected, ensuring their feasibility for resource-constrained IoD devices.

Figure 3 presents the computation overhead during various operational phases. The initialization phase shows minimal overhead for AA and RA (1.358 ms each), reflecting their efficient setup process. The registration phase incurs slightly higher overhead, particularly for RA, due to handling multiple temporary key pairs, which scales with the number of entities. During the data collection and sharing phases, the computation overhead for drones and users ranges from 2.812 ms to 4.483 ms, illustrating the computational demands of encrypting and processing data. The traceability phase introduces an overhead proportional to the number of sessions, ensuring scalability and adaptability for anomaly detection and tracking. Therefore, the findings demonstrate that the proposed scheme maintains low overheads, making it suitable for real-time IoD applications.

For comparison, Fig. 4 shows the computational efficiency of the proposed scheme against an existing scheme, Ring Learning with Errors (RLWE)-based key exchange protocol [15], which is a post-quantum key exchange protocol designed to be secure against quantum computer attacks. The proposed scheme shows a significant reduction in computational overhead. For drones, the overhead is reduced from 20 ms in the RLWE to 11.88 ms, representing 40.6% improvement. Similarly, for ground users, the overhead drops from over 10 ms to less than 7.89 ms, presenting a 21.1% improvement. These reductions are critical for ensuring IoD systems' real-time responsiveness and energy efficiency. Also, the lower overhead enables better scalability, allowing the framework to support more devices and sessions without compromising performance.

VII. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION, AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a lightweight and secure IoD framework, addressing key security, privacy, and computational efficiency challenges. By leveraging the improved FrodoKEM, a lattice-based post-quantum key encapsulation mechanism, the proposed scheme aims to achieve quantum resistance while maintaining a lightweight design suitable for resource-constrained IoD devices [16]. The framework demonstrated significant reductions in computational overhead compared

Fig. 3. Computation Overhead by Entity and Phase

Fig. 4. Comparison of Computational Overhead

to existing schemes, making it practical for real-time IoD operations. Also, it satisfies essential security properties such as implicit authentication, forward and backward secrecy, and privacy preservation, ensuring the secure exchange of data across IoD entities.

Integrating traceability mechanisms enhances accountability, allowing the detection and mitigation of malicious activities. Despite these advantages, the scheme's reliance on computationally intensive cryptographic operations like AES for symmetric encryption highlights a potential trade-off between security and performance. Future work could explore alternative lightweight encryption techniques to optimize efficiency further. The comparative analysis demonstrated that the proposed scheme significantly outperforms existing solutions regarding computational overhead, particularly for drones and ground users. However, the framework's scalability in large-scale IoD deployments remains an open question.

Future research directions include extensive evaluations of the framework's scalability in large-scale IoD deployments with varying numbers of drones, ground stations, and network conditions. Investigating alternative lightweight cryptographic primitives to replace AES is another essential avenue, aiming to reduce computational overhead without compromising security. Additionally, developing adaptive mechanisms to optimize resource allocation and communication efficiency in dynamic IoD environments, accounting for factors such as mobility and varying workloads, is essential. Exploring energy-efficient cryptographic operations to extend the operational lifetime of

drones and other IoD devices also holds significant promise.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research initiative is supported by the European Union's Horizon Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, under the TRUSTEE project (Grant Agreement No. 101070214). Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor of the granting authorities.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Badshah et al., "USAF-IoD: Ultralightweight and Secure Authenticated Key Agreement Framework for Internet of Drones Environment," in *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 73, no. 8, pp. 10963-10977, Aug. 2024.
- [2] A. Andreou, C. X. Mavromoustakis, E. K. Markakis, G. Mastorakis, E. Pallis, A. Bourdena, "Exploring Quantum-Resistant Cryptography Solutions for Health Data Exchange," in *Intelligent Technologies for Healthcare Business Applications. Signals and Communication Technology*. Springer, Cham, 2024.
- [3] Y. Liu et al., "SS-DID: A Secure and Scalable Web3 Decentralized Identity Utilizing Multilayer Sharding Blockchain," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 15, pp. 25694-25705, 1 Aug. 1, 2024.
- [4] Z. Wang, B. Cao, Y. Sun, C. Liu, Z. Wan and M. Peng, "Protecting System Information From False Base Station Attacks: A Blockchain-Based Approach," in *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 13920-13934, Oct. 2024.
- [5] A. Y. A. B. Ahmad, N. Verma, N. M. Sarhan, E. M. Awwad, A. Arora and V. O. Nyangaresi, "An IoT and Blockchain-Based Secure and Transparent Supply Chain Management Framework in Smart Cities Using Optimal Queue Model," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 51752-51771, 2024.
- [6] A. Andreou, C. X. Mavromoustakis, E. Markakis, A. Bourdena and G. Mastorakis, "On the Quantum Analysis by Using Semantic Integration and Covert Communication for Next-Generation Networks," 2024 11th International Conference on Wireless Networks and Mobile Communications (WINCOM), Leeds, United Kingdom, pp. 1-6, 2024.
- [7] M. Harmalkar, K. Jain and P. Krishnan, "A Survey of Post Quantum Key Encapsulation Mechanism," 2024 5th International Conference on Mobile Computing and Sustainable Informatics (ICMCSI), Lalitpur, Nepal, pp. 141-149, 2024.
- [8] K. Sameer, J. Neha Kishor, S. Jawar, S. Dilip and S. Anjan Kumar, "Quantum-Resistant Encryption For Secure End-to-End Communication," 2024 ITU Kaleidoscope: Innovation and Digital Transformation for a Sustainable World (ITU K), New Delhi, India, pp. 1-8, 2024.
- [9] A. K. Kwala, S. Kant and A. Mishra, "Comparative analysis of lattice-based cryptographic schemes for secure IoT communications," in *Discov Internet Things* 4, 13, 2024.
- [10] F. Samiullah, M. -L. Gan, S. Akleylek and Y. Aun, "Quantum Resistance Saber-Based Group Key Exchange Protocol for IoTs," in *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, 2024.
- [11] S. Muthupandian and D. M. Kumar, "Enhancing Security in Lightweight Healthcare Wireless Body Area Networks: Lattice-Based Cryptography framework," 2024 15th International Conference on Computing Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT), Kamand, India, pp. 1-6, 2024.
- [12] A. Andreou et al., "Enhancing Secure Communication in 6G-Enabled IoV through UAV and Control Center Integration," 2024 International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing (IWCMC), Ayia Napa, Cyprus, pp. 186-191, 2024.
- [13] C. Zhao et al., "Efficient Verifiable Dynamic Searchable Symmetric Encryption With Forward and Backward Security," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2024.
- [14] J. Bos, C. Costello, L. Ducas, I. Mironov, M. Naehrig, V. Nikolaenko, A. Raghunathan and D. Stebila, "Frodo: Take off the Ring! Practical, Quantum-Secure Key Exchange from LWE, in *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security (CCS '16)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, pp. 1006-1018, 2016.

- [15] P. Ramya, A. Pooja and K. A. Kumari, "Ensuring Health Monitoring with Smart Glucometer using Ring Learning with Errors (RLWE) and Blockchain Integration for Enhanced Security," 2024 First International Conference on Software, Systems and Information Technology (SSIT-CON), Tumkur, India, pp. 1-6, 2024.
- [16] A. Andreou, C. X. Mavromoustakis, J. M. Batalla, E. K. Markakis, G. Mastorakis and S. Mumtaz, "UAV Trajectory Optimisation in Smart Cities Using Modified A* Algorithm Combined With Haversine and Vincenty Formulas," in IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, vol. 72, no. 8, pp. 9757-9769, Aug. 2023.